

Thiopegan Derivatives. Part XXXI. Unambiguous Synthesis of 2-Substituted-9,10-thiopegan Derivatives

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2-Substituted-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-ones have been obtained by cyclisation of the corresponding 1-phenacyl-2-mercapto-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-ones, which, in turn, have been obtained from *N*-phenacylanthranilic acids and KSCN in presence of HCl.

Earlier methods¹ for the preparation of angular thiopegans mainly furnished 3-substituted derivatives except a few cases where 2,3-disubstituted compounds were obtained². In this communication we report an unambiguous route for the synthesis of 2-substituted angular thiopegans (III) for their therapeutic evaluation.

(a: R=phenyl. b: R=*p*-chlorophenyl).

Condensation of anthranilic acid with phenacetyl alcohol and its 4-chloro analogue furnished the corresponding *N*-phenacetylanthranilic acids (I, a and b) in a better state of purity and yield than the condensation of anthranilic acid with phenacetyl halides^{3,4}. The acids (I, a and b) on heating with KSCN in ethanolic solution in presence of a few drops of HCl furnished 1-phenacyl-2-mercapto-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-ones (II, a & b) which on treatment with dry HCl gas in boiling ethanolic solution cyclised to provide 2-substituted-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-ones (III, a & b).

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Phenacetylanthranilic Acid (Ia).—A solution of anthranilic acid (2.8 g.) and phenacetyl alcohol (2.7 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) was refluxed. After 10 hours' heating separation of a yellow solid started. The reaction mixture was heated for further 3 hr. and then cooled.

*Analyses are by Mr. B. N. Anand of the Punjab University Chemistry Department, Chandigarh-3.

1. Bariana *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1955, 32, 644.

2. Sharma *et al.*, *Tetrahedron* 1961 15, 53.

3. Houben and Arendt, *Ber.*, 1910, 43, 3535.

4. Scholtz, *Ber.*, 1918, 51, 1646.

The yellow product (3.5 g., 70%), m.p. 185-87°, on crystallisation from ethanol furnished rectangular plates, m.p. 190°, authenticated by comparison (m.p., mixed m.p., and phenylhydrazone) with a specimen synthesised in 42% yield by the interaction of anthranilic acid and ω -bromoacetophenone.

N-(4'-Chloro)phenacetylanthranilic Acid (I b) was prepared similarly from anthranilic acid and 4'-chlorophenacetyl alcohol (61%). Attempts at its crystallisation did not succeed and it was purified by repeated precipitation with HCl from its aqueous NaOH solution.

1-Phenacetyl-2-mercapto-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (IIa).—(a). *N*-Phenacetylanthranilic acid (Ia) (2.5 g.) and KSCN (1 g.) were ground together to a thick paste with a few drops of HCl. After about 1 hr., this paste was extracted with ethanol (2 $\times$ 25 ml) and the extract was refluxed for 20 hr. After removal of the solvent, the residue was washed with water and aqueous sodium carbonate solution. It was crystallised from ethanol as yellow plates, m.p. 173°, yield 1.2 g. (40%).

(b). A mixture of equivalent amounts of the acid (Ia) and ammonium sulphocyanide was heated in an oil bath. At 120-25°, the mixture melted and a vigorous effervescence started. The reaction mixture was heated at 140-50° for 2 hr. and worked up as in (a), yield being 25%. It did not depress the m.p. of the product obtained under (a) on admixture. The product is freely soluble in aqueous NaOH solution and could be precipitated on acidification. (Found: N, 9.74. $C_{16}H_{12}O_2N_2S$ requires N, 9.46%).

1-(4'-Chloro)phenacetyl-2-mercapto-tetrahydroquinazolin-4-one (II b) was obtained from equivalent amounts of (I b) and KSCN and a little HCl as in (a) in 30% yield. Crystallisation from ethanol furnished yellow plates, m.p. 166°. (Found: N, 8.48. $C_{16}H_{10}O_2N_2ClS$ requires N, 8.48%).

2-Phenyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (IIIa).—Dry HCl gas was passed through a boiling solution of the ketone (IIa) (2.8 g.) in ethanol (50 ml) for 8 hr. The solvent was removed by distillation. The residual solid was washed with NaOH solution and water and the product (1.0 g.) was crystallised from ethanol as brown rectangular plates, m.p. 122°. (Found: N, 9.96. $C_{16}H_{10}ON_2S$ requires N, 10.07%).

2-(4'-Chloro)phenyl-9,10-thiopega-2,10-dien-4-one (III b) was obtained similarly from (II b) in 20% yield. It was crystallised from CCl_4 as light yellow needles, m.p. 228°. (Found: N, 9.37. $C_{16}H_9ON_2ClS$ requires N, 8.84%).